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USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING GRADES 1-4 IN PRIMARY
EDUCATION.

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Abstract. This article talks about the difference between interactive methods and new textbooks and old textbooks in the teaching of primary education grades 1-4.

Key words. Education, student, independent work, educational goal, modern, PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, TAILS.

In the current era of globalization, innovations are being introduced into the field of education every day. Increasing attention is being paid to increasing the knowledge potential of young generations growing up in our society and, of course, to developing the ability to think. And in this, all the textbooks that are necessary for us have an important place. Currently, President Sh. Mirziyoyev is creating wide opportunities for young people. Education is a cooperative activity of the teacher and students, and in this process, the development of the individual, his education and upbringing is realized. In lessons, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and abilities to the students through exercises, and the students acquire the ability to use them as a result of mastering them. In the process of learning, students use different forms of learning, that is, they rely on specific differences in receiving, processing and applying the information being learned. In the course of education, issues of education and upbringing are solved in the form of cooperation between teachers and students during classes, independent work of students, extracurricular activities.

In recent years, decrees and decisions have been adopted on the organization of all stages of education based on modern requirements, and based on this, changes have been made to the basis of almost all programs and textbooks. The biggest reason for this was the fact that our national curriculum could not match the international requirements and the results of prominent educational processes abroad. The purpose of education is formed according to the needs of society. Therefore, the goal of education should be appropriate and proportionate. The goal of education in scientific literature is to create skills and competencies, develop logical-creative thinking, improve communicative literacy, inculcate the national idea, form oriental education, define personality. It is emphasized that it consists of spiritual enrichment. Based on the educational goal, students' communication culture is improved by increasing their independent thinking, oral and written literacy, and developing logical thinking. On the basis of the educational goal, spiritual, ideological and sophisticated education is provided. In the process of language learning, there is an opportunity to get closer to the cultural and moral values of the people.

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Today, the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies allows them to search for the knowledge they acquire, independent study and thinking, analysis. even teaches them to draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance.

Today, in education **"Brainstorming"**, **"Thoughtstorming"**, **"Networks" method**, **"Siquain"**, **"BBB"**, **"Fifth plus"**, **"6x6x6"**, **"Debate"**, **"Role-playing game"**, **Modern technologies such as FSMU**, **"Working in small groups"**, **"Rounded snow"**, **"Zigzag"**, **"I will say the last word"** are used.

In the process of increasing the scientific potential of children in schools, new textbooks created on the basis of best practices for grades 1-4 will be presented to them this year. These new textbooks for elementary grades are aimed at the comprehensive development of students, not only knowledge, but also the formation of skills necessary for successful adaptation to modern society. Based on foreign experiences, 72 million copies of new generation textbooks for primary classes created in 775 titles are being printed. These tutorials present an innovative approach based on the "4K" model. It helps to develop students' ability to work in a team. It helps students learn the skills of collaboration, effective communication, and mutual support.

Also, textbooks and educational methodical collections of internationally recognized publishers are being localized and published.

In particular, English, French, German, computer science and information technology textbooks are being localized and published. In addition, Cambridge physics and biology syllabuses and textbooks for grades 7-11 in specialized schools are being localized and are being prepared for publication. Taking into account that school textbooks play an extremely important role in children's general secondary education, and in order to support schoolchildren and their parents and legal representatives, and to ensure social justice, school textbooks were created at the initiative of the head of our state. and exercise books are available for free rental.

New modern school textbooks created for grades 1-4 present an innovative approach based on the "4K" model.

This methodology is aimed at comprehensive development of children and includes the following key competencies:

Collaboration: Textbooks are designed to help students develop teamwork skills. It helps students learn the skills of collaboration, effective communication, and mutual support.

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Communicativeness: Textbooks are aimed at developing students' ability to communicate with others. Students learn to express their thoughts clearly and clearly, to listen and understand the interlocutor, to effectively use language tools in conveying information.

Creative Thinking: Textbooks develop creative thinking and the ability to innovate. Students learn to use new approaches to achieve their goals, develop innovative solutions, and gain creative problem-solving skills.

Critical thinking: This methodology includes the development of students' skills to critically evaluate information, form their own opinions and judgments. Students learn to approach problems from an analytical point of view and form their own point of view based on logical thinking.

These new textbooks for elementary grades are aimed at the comprehensive development of students, not only knowledge, but also the formation of skills necessary for successful adaptation to modern society.

An important factor in the development of digital literacy of students is the purposeful and effective use of digital technologies by teachers in education, increasing the need for an individual approach, and the implementation of digital knowledge and skills.

After the educational reforms, we can see that there is a significant shift in the curriculum when comparing our National Curriculum with the International curriculum. If we take the textbooks of the old programs as an example, the previous textbooks were written in difficult academic language, which made the students bored and did not understand the subject. But today, education is based on the results of learning around the world. That is, if the student could not learn a topic in the textbook or in the program, he will study that topic again. It was not divided into hours as before. Whether the student learns or not, he moves on to the next one. As a result, the child began to hate the lesson as he did not understand. His self-esteem would decrease. That was the biggest problem. Now it is aimed not only at learning, but also at encouraging students to be ready for tomorrow's life. That is, if he can express his critical opinion in the classroom, think creatively, learn to work as a team, find a solution to a problem, make the right decision, put forward a new idea, and change the world from the point of view of science. visual perception skills are formed. In recent years, all programs and textbooks have been amended in order to solve the problems. One of these textbooks is the textbook "Native language and reading literacy" for primary classes. Winter literacy is the basis for success not only in the educational system, but also in other areas.

Mainly international programs PISA, PIRLS. Programs and textbooks that meet the requirements of studies such as TIMSS and TAILS and are based on them have been created. It is shown that the subject of mathematics is the essence of human life from the elementary

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grades. Mathematics is the science of quantitative relationships and spatial forms of the real world. Solving math problems develops students' thinking skills

According to research, a student with mathematical observation and logical thinking skills is more successful in life than a student who is good at calculus. Through this skill, a person applies mathematical knowledge in life, quickly finds solutions to various situations and problems. Taking this into account, the National Curriculum prepared on the basis of Finland, Singapore, South Korea, Great Britain and national experience focuses on the development of student's mathematical thinking. It is also based on an advanced curriculum.

For the first time in the 1st grade mathematics textbook, activities and tasks that invite our children to mathematical observation have been given ample space. Chapter 1, lesson 5 of the 1st grade mathematics textbook gives an understanding of the quantity of things, and we can see that the textbook is structured at a higher level than the previous textbook. Now in this case, the students do not count and compare the quantities, but look and think and find the solution through the adjectives. For example, he can give answers such as big-small, wide-narrow, high-low, short-long, heavy-light. Although we can see in the section of natural science, although the topics in these textbooks are a little more complicated than before, they are very interesting and understandable, and the fact that many practical exercises are given will be enjoyable for both the teacher and the student. Children of the 21st century learn these subjects without any difficulties, but with great interest. The topics given in the textbook encourage students to learn and understand real life. The picture exhibitions given for the topic "Plant organs" in chapter 2 of the textbook, such as "How does a plant feed?", "The life cycle of an apple", "The life cycle of a cucumber" are a source for easy learning by students. In particular, the practical exercise given on the topic "Study of the process of seed germination" made a vivid impression on all students. From this information, we can conclude that, first of all, it is important not only to provide students with knowledge, but also to improve them based on the knowledge they have acquired and to encourage them to think logically and critically. The main goal is to educate them so that they have the ability to apply what they have learned in life, to educate them as a mature and well-rounded person.

From this information, we can conclude that, first of all, it is important not only to give students knowledge, but also to raise them based on the knowledge they have acquired, to encourage them to think logically and critically, to educate them with the ability to apply what they have learned in life, to educate them as mature and well-rounded individuals. is the main goal.

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